

IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF NATIONAL EDUCATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOL BASED ON COLLABORATION

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Abstract. *The most important task of the school at the present stage is to teach students to independently obtain knowledge and apply it in practice. In this regard, the formation of the educational activity of schoolchildren is of particular importance. During the educational process, it is necessary to take care of the development of students' ability to learn. The effectiveness of training, as is known, is largely determined by the formation of students' skills not only to set an educational task, but also to solve it rationally, to check the correctness of the implementation.*

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In organizing the educational process during cooperation, it is important to comply with the following conditions:

- keeping diaries of psychological and pedagogical observations, recording the progress of students;
- constant verification of the effectiveness of the measures taken, implementation of their correction;
- organization of constant interaction with the parents of students in order to coordinate educational influences.

When implementing collaboration, the teacher must be guided by the following requirements:

- create an atmosphere favorable for students;
- actively communicate with students, because in order for the educational process to be motivated and for the child to study according to his individual capabilities and characteristics, he must clearly imagine and understand what is expected of him[2].

This provision seems important not only because students know the expectations of their teachers, but they need to be told how they learn. Feedback provides a strong basis for motivation. In working with students, we suggest the following strategy of collaboration in pedagogical actions:

- direct influence on motivation through persuasion, explanation and stimulation of internal work on self-awareness, rethinking of oneself and the surrounding reality;
- influence on motivation through high organization of educational and cognitive activity of schoolchildren. The learning objectives for each group of children are differentiated.

Objectives of intellectual development:

For children with a high level:

- development of intellectual qualities of personality, independence and creative thinking;
- improvement of subject skills and abilities;
- development of creative and research skills;

- formation of the need for independent cognitive activity;
- mastering the skills of self-reflection.

For children with an average level:

- development of cognitive mental processes;
- creation of psychological and pedagogical conditions for the transition to a higher level;
- formation and development of skills and abilities in the subject.

For children with a low level:

- formation and correction of motivational attitudes towards educational activities;
- development of mental work skills that allow for complete acquisition of basic knowledge

and create opportunities for moving to the second level;

- development of intellectual qualities: voluntary attention and perception, conscious thinking, logical memory, etc.

Collaborative learning is characterized by:

1. In a high-level group:

- learning the technology of searching for new knowledge, working with additional sources of information;

- developing self-control skills for learning knowledge;

- engaging in search activities, using creative tasks, solving non-standard problems.

2. In the middle-level group:

- learning the technology of searching for new knowledge, working with a textbook;

- organizing independent activities of a reproductive and partially search nature, self-monitoring the acquisition of knowledge;

- selecting methods that facilitate the acquisition of knowledge at a partially search level.

3. In the low-level group:

creation of positive motivation through practical orientation of training, connection with life, orientation towards success, registration of real progress in training;

- creation of conditions allowing each student to assess his/her position and consider possibilities for its improvement;

- selection of methods facilitating acquisition of basic knowledge at the reproductive level, but also application of partial-search and problem-based teaching methods in appropriate situations;

- formation of thinking actions and operations; teaching of subject actions and skills not only at the empirical level, but also, if possible, at the theoretical level.

With a differentiated approach, the following conditions for collaboration in the educational and cognitive activity of students are successful [5]:

- creating a situation of success and confidence for the student;
- cooperation between the teacher and the student;
- creating a situation for the student when he can choose the level of complexity and difficulty of the test task;

- the teacher can choose the form of the control procedure;

- taking into account the time factor depending on the individual capabilities of the student;

- thematic accounting of knowledge;

- using the small group method;

- logical conditioning of the timeliness of control;

- guaranteeing the student the right to improve the grade;
- compliance with the principle of humanization in the implementation of control;
- encouraging the student;
- compliance of the goals of control with the goals of the educational process.

Methods and techniques of differentiation. An individual approach to children in organizing educational activities is implemented through tasks of varying volume, varying degrees of difficulty, varying degrees of assistance provided through instructions. At the same time, as a teacher, I take into account the characteristics inherent in children of different typological groups, and the characteristics of general speech development, memory, children's interests, as well as the child's progress in mastering the program material[6].

When organizing the educational work of children with a predominance of inhibition over excitation in the nervous processes, I provide for tasks aimed at developing speech. So that children in this group firmly assimilate the educational material, since they need repeated repetitions of what they have learned. I include tasks of an advanced nature, as well as tasks using a plan, which allows for making the process of perception more dismembered, overcoming the poverty of perception that schoolchildren have [8].

To organize the educational work of children with a predominance of excitation over inhibition in the nervous processes, I select exercises that are small in volume (so that the child can see the end of the task), varied in content, since these children need tasks that require analysis using reminders.

Tasks for the largest group of students with balanced nervous processes of excitation and inhibition are creative in nature, developing and deepening the child's inclinations and interests. Let's consider various methods of differentiation that can be used in the lesson at the stage of consolidation of the studied material. They involve differentiation of the content of educational tasks by the level of creativity, difficulty, volume.

Using different methods of organizing children and common tasks, I differentiate them by:

- the degree of independence of students;
- the nature of assistance to students;
- the form of educational activities.

Differentiation methods can be combined with each other, and tasks can be offered to students to choose from.

1. Collaborative learning tasks based on the level of creativity. This method of differentiation presupposes differences in the nature of students' cognitive activity, which can be reproductive or productive (creative).

Reductive tasks include, for example, solving familiar types of problems, finding the values of expressions based on studied computational techniques, etc. Students are required to reproduce knowledge and apply it in a normal situation, work according to a model, and perform training exercises.

Productive tasks include exercises that differ from standard ones. Students have to apply knowledge in a changed or new, unfamiliar situation, perform more complex mental actions (for example, search, transformation), create a new product (make equalities or inequalities, etc.). In the process of working on productive tasks, schoolchildren gain experience in creative activity [15].

2. Collaborative educational tasks by difficulty level.

This method of differentiation involves the following types of complication of tasks for the most prepared students:

- complication of educational material;
- increase in the number of actions in an expression or in solving a problem;
- performing a comparison operation in addition to the main task;
- using an inverse task instead of a direct one;
- using conditional symbols (“fairy-tale numbers”, letters) instead of numbers.

3. Collaboration of tasks by volume of educational material.

This method of differentiation involves completing an additional task.

The need to differentiate tasks by volume is due to the different pace of students' work. Slow children, as well as children with a low level of learning ability, usually do not have time to complete independent work by the time of its frontal check in class; they need additional time for this. The rest of the children spend this time completing the additional task.

As a rule, differentiation by volume is usually combined with other methods of differentiation. As additional ones, I offer creative or more difficult tasks, as well as tasks that are not related in content to the main one, for example, from other sections of the program. Additional tasks can be tasks on ingenuity, non-standard tasks, and game-like exercises [12].

4. Collaborative work based on the students' level of independence.

This method of differentiation does not imply differences in learning tasks for different groups of students. All children perform the same exercises, but some do it under the guidance of a teacher, while others do it independently.

At the orientation stage, students get acquainted with the task, find out its meaning and rules of execution. After this, some children begin to independently complete the task. The rest, with the help of the teacher, analyze the solution method or the proposed sample, and perform part of the exercise frontally. As a rule, this is enough for another part of the children to begin working independently. Those students who still have difficulties in their work complete the entire task under the guidance of the teacher. The verification stage is carried out independently. Thus, the degree of independence of the students varies. The students themselves determine at what stage they should begin to complete the task independently. If necessary, they can return to work under the guidance of the teacher at any time.

5. Collaborative work by the nature of assistance to students. This method, unlike differentiation by the degree of independence, does not provide for the organization of frontal work under the guidance of a teacher. All students immediately begin independent work. But those children who experience difficulties in completing the task are given dosed assistance.

The most common types of assistance are:

- assistance in the form of auxiliary tasks, preparatory exercises;
- assistance in the form of “hints” (assistant cards, consultation cards, notes on the board, etc.).

Stimulating, guiding and educational assistance is used.

I suggest that students with a high level of learning ability complete the task independently, and I provide assistance of varying levels to students with average and low levels of learning ability. It is important to take into account that the degree of assistance to the student decreases from lesson to lesson. In the end, he should learn to complete the tasks independently, without any assistance [4].

Various types of assistance can be used on the cards:

- a sample of completing the task: showing the solution method, a sample of reasoning (for example, in the form of a detailed record of the solution to the example) and design;
- reference materials: theoretical information in the form of a rule, formula; - tables of units of length, mass, etc.;
- algorithms, reminders, plans, instructions (for example, an algorithm for dividing a multi-digit number by a single-digit number in writing in the form of a reminder);
- visual aids, illustrations, models (for example, a brief record of the problem, a graphic diagram, a table, etc.);
- additional specification of the task (for example, an explanation of individual words in the problem, an indication of some detail essential for solving the problem);
- auxiliary (leading) questions, direct or indirect instructions for completing the task;
- a plan for solving the problem;
- the beginning of a solution or a partially completed solution.

Different types of assistance when a student completes one task are often combined with each other.

6. Collaborative work on the form of educational activities.

In the works of N.F. Talyzina, various forms of educational activities are considered in detail. Let us describe their main features.

1. Object actions are usually performed by hand. This is a real transformation of an object with the purpose of studying its properties. The action can be material (various objects are used, for example, counting material) or materialized (substitutes, models, i.e. sign-symbolic means are used).

2. The perceptual action is performed not by the hand, but by the eye. The transformation of real or symbolic objects is carried out without the use of objective actions.

3. The speech action can be carried out as loud speech (saying the operations being performed out loud or in a whisper) external speech to oneself (silent pronunciation of the action to oneself, but with a clear verbal-conceptual division of it).

4. Mental action is carried out without relying on any external means, in the internal plane. The speech shell is reduced, acquires the character of internal speech. The action is performed in the mind. When organizing work, for example, with mathematical material, the teacher can differentiate the nature of the educational actions performed by children, relying on the following logic of complicating their form: subject, perceptual, mental action. Children who need speech actions are offered to pronounce the operations performed, for example, whisper to yourself how to calculate; explain to a neighbor on the desk how to reason when solving a word problem [13].

Different methods of differentiation are usually used in combination with each other. I consider the following organization of work to be the most appropriate: children with an average level of learning ability perform a training exercise from the textbook independently, children with a low level of learning ability perform the same exercise under the guidance of a teacher or independently using assistant cards. Children with a high level of learning ability are offered a creative task or more difficult one compared to the task in the textbook [14].

Thus, children receive quite extensive information even before the lesson. This allows more attention to be paid to the implementation of developmental goals, since this content is

systematized and generalized. To activate cognitive interest in studying nature, developing independence, I also use the following technique.

There are also many techniques in my practice that would allow organizing the consolidation of the studied material. But I would like to dwell on one technique. At the end of the lesson, I sometimes practice writing mini-essays on the topic covered. Moreover, if the students did not manage to finish it in the lesson, they do it at home.

Thus, with differentiated teaching, homework assignments are more valuable in the methodological respect, in which the didactic material initially has the character of general exercises for the whole class, in addition, the assignments also contain additional questions and tasks that deepen the understanding of educational material of the main program. If, when performing differentiated homework, less advanced students achieve positive results, then they are offered advanced level assignments or creative assignments.

An individual approach to students creates conditions for completing assignments aimed at deepening the knowledge acquired in class, improving skills and abilities, as well as assignments taking into account the interests and inclinations of the child. This applies primarily to homework. Such additional assignments stimulate students' cognitive activity and help them maintain faith in their abilities and strengths. However, the element of voluntary choice of such an assignment remains [5].

In the educational process, the child must be constantly accompanied by a sense of free choice, there must be scope for creativity, intelligence, independence. This does not mean freedom of action, and, therefore, spontaneous development. The provision on providing the child with free choice in the educational process means the following: the child himself chooses any task. It is known that children do better and more willingly the work that they themselves have chosen:

- Do any exercise on the page.
- Read any story by the writer.

The ability of collaboration of younger schoolchildren to exercise freedom of choice of tasks largely depends on the wealth of experience that they acquire in the process of learning. Practice shows that younger schoolchildren usually choose more complex tasks.

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